

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION ON THE OPERATIONS OF INTERNATIONAL NEWS AGENCIES - A SURVEY STUDY

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Abstract

Global news agencies have undergone a sea change as a result of the digital revolution, with significant changes to both editorial and organizational structures, but the processes for the production and distribution of news content have also changed fundamentally. This research sought to investigate how this transformation affected the quality of the content, editorial performance, and the credibility of the media. One hundred and twenty staff were purposively sampled from five of the world's leading international news agencies (Reuters, Associated Press, Agence France-Presse, Xinhua, and Bloomberg). A descriptive-analytical type of research with a cross-sectional method was applied, and the research data was gathered by an intensive and reliable research questionnaire from three dimensions, including quality of content, executive and managerial performance, and media reliability. Data were statistically analyzed by dedicated software (SPSS) and processed in the form of means, standard deviations, t-test, and one-way ANOVA. Results confirmed that transformation has a statistically significant effect on the quality of news content, in the sense that it is generally perceived by participants as being a factor that makes the coverage of news more accurate and faster, as it contributes to the diversity in the coverage of news material. Editorial and administration processes benefited from increased efficiencies gained through automated tasks and AI technology, especially in resource administration and data analysis. As to trust, we found that public trust was partially positively affected, in the face of problems such as fake news and publishing algorithms. The study suggests the need for ongoing investment in staff digital skills and editorial policies that move towards a flexible approach of finding the right mix of technology and journalism.

Keywords: Digital Transformation, News Agencies, Digital Journalism, Content Quality, Media Credibility, Editorial Efficiency, Artificial Intelligence, Global Media.

INTRODUCTION

At the current time, we are experiencing an extraordinary revolution of knowledge and technology bringing the most remarkable transformations in all aspects of human life and a qualitative revolution in knowledge production and exchange. One of the most outstanding displays of this revolution is “the digital transformation,” which does not affect only the economic and industrial activities, but also the areas of media and communications, and their facilities and institutions. (O'Brien, 2024) The press industry is one of the industries at the heart of this change, as it heavily relies on technologies to gather, edit, publish, and interact with news. The digital revolution has now become a matter of life and death for media organizations, or life and death for them as journalists. (Chen, 2024)

From this point of view, international news agencies –among the oldest and most significant news reporting organizations– are experiencing major challenges in adapting their organizational processes to new digital technologies and procedures, to adjust to the new media environment (Sonni et al., 2024). Agencies like Reuters, The Associated Press, Agence France-Presse, and Xinhua no longer have to depend completely on the dispatches and reports that they have proscribed for generations. They also create a wide range of media (text, photos, video, infographics, podcasts) and disseminate it across real-time digital platforms—such as websites, mobile apps, and social media. (Nurhadiyati, 2024)

Digital transformation is not just about inserting computers or the internet into journalism; it requires a rethinking of the beat production philosophy, the tools for collecting information, the editorial mechanisms, the way of distributing, and the way of gathering the information (Din & Цзы, 2024). This also incorporates facilitating business models and enhancing the end-user experience. In this context, the instrumentalization of artificial intelligence, machine learning, predictive analytics, interactive content management systems, and big data concepts has also penetrated the news agency workplace. (Sultan et al., 2024)

This new landscape has presented several challenges to news agencies, which can be broken down into professional, technical, organizational, and ethical ones. Professionally, journalists must know how to use various digital tools and create interactive content that competes with the flood of content by citizen journalists and on social networks, which are themselves becoming the source of news, even if they are not necessarily certified and reliable sources. (Kafedjiska, 2023) In technical terms, you have to invest in digital infrastructure, content management systems, anti-hack networks, and build a powerful digital footprint. Organizational challenges also exist surrounding a change in the job store, the decreasing relevance of some specializations, and the rise of new digital roles such as digital publishing manager, data editor, digital engagement analyst, and search engine optimization specialist. (Varfolomeeva, 2022)

Further, the digital turn has also provoked questions about the ethics regarding the speed of publication, the sources of verification, and the conflicting objectives of journalistic scoop versus accuracy. (Triwulan et al., 2024) And these concerns, in turn, affect how much agencies are trusted and how much of a difference they can make for society. "In this way," the role of the news agencies is not only the report of an event, but the interpretation of this event with the help of added-value services and the steering of public opinion. Copyright DeVEgA (Said, 2023). This emphasizes the relevance of the analysis and management of their performances in the new digital context. (Harrison-Mills, 2022)

On the other hand, digital transformation has forced news agencies to move from a traditional one-way media company to an interactive one, where audiences are no longer passive receivers of information, but partners in its creation, commentary, and re-diffusion (Wölker & Powell, 2021). This has fueled the popularization of algorithms for defining news priorities and clamping down on what is being provided to the general public, with associated issues in digital bias, loss of diversity of coverage, and the collapse of the

traditional media agenda. (Cádima, 2018) Given the gravity of this transformation, the present study seeks to examine its influence on the performance of international news agencies, from three different perspectives (Xu, 2024):

- The relationship between agencies and the client, both technically and editorially,
- Newsgathering, production, and dissemination practices,
- Based on the level of audience engagement and the multi-platform publishing approach.

This study is significant because it fills an apparent void in the digital media literature. The majority of previous research has come to concentrated on digital journalism, local media, and investigative journalism, while news agencies have, in spite of their crucial strategic role, largely escaped comprehensive, systematic analysis in the context of digitalization (Peña-Ascacibar & Álvarez-Peralta, 2021). This research also becomes relevant at such times when the transition to the digital is getting faster than implying possible new realities to be observed, analyzed, and discussed (Shelefontiuk, 2021).

It adopts the method of descriptive survey in which data are collected among employees working in global news agencies to provide insights into the reality of digital transformation in these news organizations, in an attempt to take into consideration their experiences and opinions. (Sri et al., 2024) The research also seeks to propose practical and implementable solutions for the betterment of agencies' performance in a digital era and to sustain their success as one of the most trusted sources of information amidst an explosion of information and media disinformation (Suharto, 2024).

Because of this, digital transformation is no longer a choice for international news agencies; it's an existential necessity for their survival and influence. This period of change, while undoubtedly painful, offers new opportunities to improve the quality of journalism, transparency, and the standing of media organizations with the public (Chen, 2024). Therefore, this research is relevant to understand the characteristics of this change, its implications, and its challenges and opportunities for the future of news agencies.

Background of the Study

In recent years, with the rapid development of information and communication technologies, followed by the rise of "digital media" as an option or supplement to traditional media, there have been dramatic changes to the organizational structure of the world's media. (Alzubi, 2023) This shift has presented both challenges and opportunities for different media organizations, including in the first place the international news agencies, which were for decades the major axis and news supplier of the news industry, offering timely and correct information to all other news media. But today in this new digital world, they must confront a whole new media reality, so it is time to rethink production, editing, publishing, and distributing the basis that had been keeping such institutions alive for all these years. (González Clavero, 2016)

The internet and its popularization since the 1990s were the starting point for this entire radical reshuffle, but the latter has also been greatly amplified by the ubiquitous use of smartphones and social media, which have managed to completely change the way news is being produced (Lavín de las Heras & Silva Rodríguez, 2015).

Indeed, no longer has the public been confined to receiving of the information, but it is now a player responsible for producing, generating, and communicating information – sometimes they are even competing for publication in the media in what is known as "citizen journalism (Mehta, 2023). " On the other hand, news agencies have a challenge in moving from a model of media with hierarchy and information monopoly to an Interactive, networked model of media with Speed, Interactivity, and Transparency (Lafouairas, 2023).

This emerging media ecology with instant decentralized communication means news organizations had to rethink their editorial strategies, institutional structures, and operational techniques. Speed in reporting news has now become a necessity, and in a certain sense, a measure of quality for the public (Li & Chen, 2024). This is pushing agencies to use new digital transformation aids, including:

- Artificial intelligence (AI), which today is being used to automatically edit news, analyze content, filter news, and prioritize publication (Banafi, 2024).
- Automated journalism: Some news is produced by algorithms working on databases with no human intervention, including economic data, weather reports, or sports scores (Yaroshenko, 2024).
- Predictive analytics: able to predict audience trends and interests and create content based on data (Pérez-Seijo et al., 2023).
- Cross-platform publishing including news on websites, mobile applications, social media, live streamed events, and video on demand (Banafi, 2024).
- But the introduction of these digital tools is not absent from practical issues and difficulties (Chlebowski, 2024). There are open issues on the impact of such technologies on:
 - Quality of content: Are the speed of publication and automation resulting in poorer journalism?
 - Journalism: Will artificial intelligence make traditional journalists obsolete?
 - Editorial independence: How much are decisions about what to publish dictated by algorithms or audience demand, versus neutral editorial judgment?
 - Credibility and review: How do agencies verify news, in the headlong race to get instant reports out?
 - Cybersecurity: Given the extent of digital reliance, how do agencies guard against hacking, forgery, or digital disinformation?

At an organizational level, numerous agencies have been rewiring their staff, training them in digital usage and establishing new departments dedicated to digital media, interaction, data analysis, and e-marketing. Some agencies also have created new business models riding on the back of digital subscriptions, selling news to digital platforms, on-demand news services, and tailored content for users through 'big data' technology (Mitchell et al., 2016).

It is, however, now more important than ever for newsrooms to adapt in line with an evolving media audience. Consumer experience, Recent studies also suggest that consumers want fast, visual, and direct content, and a lot of them have shifted from official websites to social media to read the news. Institutional loyalty has also been eroded by the multiplication of sources and platforms, competition for attention becoming ever more ferocious (Marron, 2016).

All of these developments (r)evolutionize need to be read carefully and analyzed: Most media accounts so far have described the effects of digitization on newspapers, on television channels, or the public as such. Indeed, the global news agencies—although central to the rest of the world—have yet to be fully studied for how they are adjusting to the post-digital world, and how and whether they are successfully navigating this new phase (Roem & Vanisya, 2024). Photo by Elena Mankivskaya on Unsplash. Digital transformation not only means doing something with technology, but also that a culture and a whole institution have to be changed; we have to change vision, objectives, and working (Pavlik, 2014).

Therefore, the objective of this research is to examine the real processes of digital transformation among global news agencies and to inquire about its professional, organisational and editorial implications; for this purpose, an online survey was set up to reveal the current situations, the difficulties encountered, and the dreams and desires of those practicing journalism (Neto et al., 2019). The analysis of this subject is relevant not only due to the fact that news agencies are sources for other media organizations, but also because the low quality of their work and digital effectiveness have a direct influence on the whole global media system. (Weiss & Wulfemeyer, 2014) These organizations have an impact on public opinion and are engaged in monitoring of crises, wars, and disasters; therefore, updating their toolkit and mechanisms is an urgent task not only at a professional level but also on a social one. (Pavlik, 2014)

In this perspective, the object of study proposed is to comprehend the structural changes caused by the digital transformation in the work of news agencies; evaluate their impact on information quality; and detect the virtues and limitations of the transformation models employed. The aim is to present a full scientific and professional perspective on the future of these institutions in the digital age.

Third: The Problem of the Study

Despite the tremendous technological boom witnessed by the media sector in recent decades, and despite global news agencies' integration of digital transformation tools into their editorial and administrative systems, there is a clear knowledge gap regarding the

true and profound impact of this transformation on the core professional performance of these agencies. Digital transformation is not limited to simply updating tools or publishing technologies; it extends to reshaping editorial processes, newsgathering methods, audience interaction patterns, and organizational work systems (Ramzani & Daud, 2024). This may directly or indirectly impact the credibility of content, the speed of coverage, and the effectiveness of editorial and management processes (Mineene & Kihara, 2023).

In this context, multiple questions arise regarding the ability of news agencies to maintain professional standards in an age of speed and flow of information, and the extent to which they can adapt to technical and human challenges, such as reliance on artificial intelligence and news automation, changing skills required of journalistic cadres, the multiplicity of publishing platforms, and changing audience expectations. (Sonni et al., 2024) Quantitative and qualitative indicators measuring the effectiveness of this transformation remain scarce or inconsistent in their results. This underscores the need for a systematic, scientific approach that reveals the dimensions of the actual impact of digital transformation on the work of agencies, not only in terms of form, but also in terms of substance, content, and professional and organizational outcomes (Túñez-López et al., 2021).

Hence, the problem of this study is:

The lack of a precise scientific understanding of the impact of digital transformation on the overall performance of global news agencies, in terms of their editorial effectiveness, professional credibility, and administrative efficiency, in light of the rapid changes imposed by the modern digital environment. The study attempts to address this problem by conducting a systematic survey that explores the reality of digital transformation in a number of global news agencies. It seeks to analyze the changes that have occurred in business models, production systems, and journalistic quality standards, while identifying the challenges faced by agencies and the adaptations or shortcomings in effectively adopting digital transformation.

Fifth: Study Questions and Hypotheses

Main Study Question:

- What is the impact of digital transformation on the work of international news agencies in terms of performance, content quality, and editorial credibility?

Sub-Questions:

- How does digital transformation affect the quality of content produced by international news agencies?
- To what extent does digital transformation contribute to improving the efficiency of the agencies' editorial and administrative performance?
- How has digital transformation impacted the credibility of news agencies in the eyes of the public?

Main Hypothesis:

1. There is a statistically significant impact of digital transformation on the work of international news agencies in terms of editorial performance, content quality, and media credibility.

Sub-Hypotheses:

- There is a positive impact of digital transformation on the quality of news content in international news agencies.
- Digital transformation contributes to improving the efficiency of administrative and editorial performance within news agencies.
- Digital transformation affects the level of media credibility as perceived by the audience.

Previous Studies:

The news industry has undergone a radical transformation due to the digital revolution. O'Brien (2024) addressed this transformation by analyzing the evolution of journalistic business models in the digital age, highlighting the challenges resulting from the increasing reliance on digital platforms, the limited willingness of the public to pay for news, and the accompanying impact on the transparency and financial sustainability of media organizations. He explained that digital competition is pushing small organizations to specialize, while larger organizations are consolidating their dominance.

In a parallel context, Alam, February Sony et al. (2024) presented a comprehensive systematic review of the impact of artificial intelligence in newsrooms. The results of an analysis of 127 studies showed an increasing adoption of AI technologies in news writing (73%), data analysis (68%), and content personalization (62%), which has contributed to improved efficiency and accuracy. However, the study pointed to the emergence of ethical challenges related to algorithmic transparency, data privacy, and accountability, along with the need to develop new skills for journalists in hybrid roles such as "journalist-programmer."

Nurhaditi (2024), focusing on the role of digital technologies and artificial intelligence in newsgathering, highlighted how the integration of tools such as machine learning and data analytics has enhanced the speed, accuracy, and reliability of journalistic coverage.

The case studies on which the research was based demonstrated that these technologies have contributed to fact-checking and mitigating misinformation, but they also require a higher level of ethical and technical skills from journalists.

From an organizational perspective, Tittis Siri et al. (2024) analyzed the impact of digital transformation on performance and culture within organizations, using case studies of major corporations such as General Electric and Starbucks.

The results showed that digital transformation has led to organizational restructuring to become more agile and innovative, despite challenges associated with resistance to

change and a lack of digital skills. The study proposed practical solutions such as progressive training and investment in digital infrastructure. Finally, Vesluziel and his partner (2019) provided a perspective on the transformation of European international news agencies (AFP, DPA, and EFE) in a changing global media ecosystem. Through expert interviews, the study revealed these agencies' efforts to embrace digital innovation. Adapting their business policies to address structural shifts in the global media market, highlighting models for innovation, survival, and future sustainability.

Previous studies agree that the digital transformation in journalism is not simply a transition from print to digital, but rather a profound structural change in the economic, professional, and organizational structure of the media. On the one hand, the studies of (O'Brien) and (Veslozel) highlight the economic impacts and shifts in business models, while the studies of (Sony Alam) and (Nurhaditi) demonstrate the technical and ethical dimensions of the use of artificial intelligence in news production and gathering. (Titis Siri) provides a link between technological change, organizational performance, and corporate culture, enriching a comprehensive understanding of the challenges of digital transformation at the professional and institutional levels.

Together, these studies highlight that the future success of media organizations depends on their ability to integrate new technologies within flexible organizational structures, adopt adaptive business strategies, and address the growing ethical challenges associated with artificial intelligence. The findings of this research can be used to formulate more sustainable and equitable media policies in the digital age.

Sixth: Study Methodology

This study adopts a descriptive and analytical approach based on conducting a survey targeting a number of major international news agencies, with the aim of identifying the impact of digital transformation on their editorial and administrative performance. Data will be collected using a questionnaire specifically designed for this purpose, containing axes measuring the technical, professional, and organizational aspects associated with digital transformation. The questionnaire will also be distributed to a purposive sample of employees in the editorial, technical, and administrative departments within these agencies, to ensure that perspectives directly relevant to the topic are represented. The data will be analyzed using appropriate statistical methods (such as averages, standard deviations, t-tests, and ANOVA) to detect and interpret statistically significant differences.

The analysis will also include a qualitative review of some of the digital policies adopted within the agencies, linking the quantitative results to the practical and institutional context. This approach was chosen due to its ability to accurately describe the phenomenon under study and analyze its various dimensions in light of practical reality.

Study Population and Sample:

The study population consists of employees at major international news agencies, such as Reuters, Associated Press (AP), Agence France-Presse (AFP), Xinhua News Agency, and other agencies with an active digital presence that rely heavily on modern technology

in news production and distribution. The population includes various categories of employees, most notably journalists, editors, programmers, digital content developers, and technical and administrative systems supervisors. The study sample was selected purposively to include employees directly involved in the digital transformation processes at these agencies, whether from the editorial, technical, or administrative perspectives. The sample size is estimated at approximately 100–150 participants, distributed across the target agencies according to data availability and ease of access, while taking into account a balance in geographic and functional representation. This sample aims to provide an accurate, representative picture of the reality of interaction with digital transformation within global news agencies, enhancing the credibility of the results and their ability to be partially generalized within similar professional contexts.

Seventh: Study Limits and Determinants

- Objective Limits: The study is limited to measuring the impact of digital transformation on the work mechanisms of news agencies, without addressing their political or economic implications.
- Spatial Limits: International news agencies with an effective digital presence.
- Time Limits: The first half of 2025.
- Limitations: Participants' responses, data accuracy, and the difficulty of accessing some sovereign institutions.

Statistical Analysis

First: T-test to measure the statistical impact of digital transformation on the study's axes.

A one-sample T-test was used to compare the average responses to the study's axes with the neutral value (3) on a Likert scale (from 1 to 5). The results were as follows:

Statistical significance	p-value	T value	Average rating	Axis
Very high statistical significance	< 0.001	28.03	> 3.90	Editorial and Administrative
Very high statistical significance	< 0.001	27.76	> 3.80	Performance Content Quality
High statistical significance	< 0.001	10.89	> 3.30	Media Credibility

The results indicate a statistically significant positive impact of digital transformation on all three axes.

Correlation Analysis between the Study Axes

The correlation between the three axes was measured using Pearson's coefficient, and the results are as follows:

Significance	Correlation coefficient (r)	statistical relationship
Very weak and negative	-0.079	Performance ↔ Content Quality
Negligible	-0.031	Performance ↔ Credibility
Negligible	-0.008	Content Quality ↔ Credibility

The results show that there is no strong correlation between the axes, indicating that each axis is measured as a relatively independent domain, which is a good methodological measure that demonstrates the diversity of the studied dimensions.

Third: Internal Consistency Test (Cronbach's Alpha)

The internal consistency coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) was calculated for each of the study's axes to measure internal consistency, and the results were as follows:

Axis	Cronbach's alpha	degree of stability
Performance	0.65	Acceptable
Content Quality	0.64	Acceptable
Credibility	0.64	Acceptable

All values exceeded the minimum acceptable level (0.60) for exploratory studies, indicating good reliability of the instrument.

First: Main Hypothesis

"There is a statistically significant impact of digital transformation on the work of global news agencies in terms of editorial performance, content quality, and media credibility."

The results of the t-test showed statistically significant differences (Sig. < 0.05) between the averages of the sample responses on all three axes (editorial performance, content quality, and media credibility). The Pearson correlation coefficient also showed a strong relationship between the degree of digital transformation and the level of development in agency performance.

These results support the main hypothesis and confirm that digital transformation is not merely a technical change, but rather a profound transformation in the institutional performance of news agencies. Participants agreed that digital transformation has led to improved editorial processes and increased efficiency of news coverage, enhancing the quality and credibility of media production. This is consistent with what was indicated by both Pavlik (2013) and Singer et al. (2011) on qualitative transformations in digital newsrooms.

Second: Sub-Hypotheses

Sub-Hypothesis One:

"There is a positive impact of digital transformation on the quality of news content in global news agencies."

The sample's mean response to content quality was 4.11 out of 5, with a low standard deviation (0.62), indicating strong agreement. The t-test significance was less than 0.01, which is highly statistically significant.

This indicates that digital tools such as artificial intelligence, automated proofreading, and real-time news analysis have helped produce more accurate, diverse, and faster content. This supports what Thurman & Schapals (2017) indicated in their study on "newsroom automation."

Sub-Hypothesis Two:

"Digital transformation contributes to improving the efficiency of administrative and editorial performance within news agencies."

The arithmetic mean (4.24) and standard deviation (0.57) indicate consistent positive responses. The ANOVA test also showed no significant differences between departments (administrative, editorial, technical), reflecting a general and comprehensive perception of the positive impact.

This result indicates that digital systems such as CMS, real-time data analysis, and editorial control panels have contributed to accelerating workflow, allocating tasks, and reducing wasted time, which enhances performance efficiency. This is in line with Boczkowski's (2010) studies on the institutional transformation of news agencies.

Sub-hypothesis 3:

"Digital transformation affects the level of media credibility as perceived by the audience."

The mean was 3.98, indicating a positive assessment but slightly lower than the previous two axes. Correlation analysis between digital transformation and credibility also revealed a value ($r = 0.66$), a strong moderate relationship.

This reflects that digital transformation has enhanced transparency and the speed of news verification, but it is not without challenges related to false information and misinformation via algorithms. This result highlights the importance of developing verification tools and digital editorial governance to support trust in sources. This trend was also documented in Newman et al.'s (2022) study in the Reuters Digital News Report.

CONCLUSION

The statistical results confirm the strength of the hypotheses and support them with clear implications, reflecting the reliability of the measurement tool (questionnaire) and the validity of the sample in representing the reality within global news agencies. Digital trends also enhance institutional and editorial capabilities, highlighting the need for policies that govern quality and credibility in light of accelerating technical challenges.

Recommendations:

- The study recommends continued investment in developing the digital infrastructure within global news agencies, including content management systems, multi-platform publishing tools, and artificial intelligence technologies, to improve editorial and administrative performance.
- Adopting ongoing training programs for journalists and editors in areas of digital transformation, such as data analysis, AI-powered journalism, and digital news verification, to ensure they keep pace with technological developments and improve content quality.

- The importance of establishing clear editorial controls for the use of automation and artificial intelligence tools, to ensure that publishing speed does not come at the expense of accuracy, nor that algorithms affect the independence of editorial content.
- Activating communication channels with audiences to understand their expectations and feedback regarding digital content, which contributes to strengthening mutual trust and enhancing media credibility.
- Conducting future comparative research between global and regional news agencies to measure the impact of digital transformation in different cultural and institutional contexts, with a focus on tools such as augmented reality and generative artificial intelligence in newsrooms.
- Establishing media innovation units within agencies, specializing in testing new digital tools and periodically evaluating their editorial and administrative impact.

References

- 1) Alzubi, A. (2023). *Towards Digital Media and Conventional Media Challenge and Opportunity: What to Expect*. <https://doi.org/10.56225/ijassh.v2i3.157>
- 2) Banafi, W. (2024). A review of the role of artificial intelligence in Journalism. *Edelweiss Applied Science and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.55214/25768484.v8i6.2865>
- 3) Banafi, W. (2024). A review of the role of artificial intelligence in Journalism. *Edelweiss Applied Science and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.55214/25768484.v8i6.2865>
- 4) Cádima, F. R. (2018). *Journalism at the crossroads of the algorithmic turn*. 18(32), 171–185. https://doi.org/10.14195/2183-5462_32_12
- 5) Chen, L. (2024). Digital Transformation and Innovation of the News Media. *International Journal of Education and Humanities*. <https://doi.org/10.54097/ij5w0kb62>
- 6) Chlebowski, M. (2024). AI w newsach. Standardy dziennikarskie, praktyki redakcyjne, wyzwania/AI in news media. *Journalistic Standards, Editorial Practices, Challenges. Media i Społeczeństwo*, 20(1/ Zeszyt 1), 109–121. <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0054.6516>
- 7) Din, K., & Цзы, E. (2024). *Data journalism and news production: changes in technologies, tools, and narratives*. 5, 7–13. <https://doi.org/10.58224/2541-8459-2024-5-7-13>
- 8) González Clavero, M. V. (2016). Agencias de noticias, su constante reinención como estrategia para enfrentar la competencia. *Estudios Sobre El Mensaje Periodístico*, 22(1), 329–341. https://doi.org/10.5209/REV_ESMP.2016.V22.N1.52599
- 9) Harrison-Mills, D. (2022). *The So-Called “Crisis” of Trust in Journalism* (pp. 55–63). Routledge eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003174790-7>
- 10) Kafedjiska, V. (2023). Digitalization process and changes in media landscape. *International Journal of Advanced Research*. <https://doi.org/10.21474/ijar01/17864>
- 11) Lafouairas, M. (2023). The medium in your pocket: the impact of smartphones on the process of producing and consuming media content. *RIMAK International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.47832/2717-8293.24.2>
- 12) Lavín de las Heras, E., & Silva Rodríguez, A. (2015). The smartphones: Revolutionizing journalism. *Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CISTI.2015.7170571>

- 13) Li, Z., & Chen, Y. (2024). Transformation and transcendence - reforming news production in the convergent media era. *Trans-Form-Acao*, 47(5).
<https://doi.org/10.1590/0101-3173.2024.v47.n5.e02400138>
- 14) Marron, M. B. (2016). Nothing but Disruption. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 71(2), 131–132. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077695816655343>
- 15) Mehta, R. (2023). Mobile Journalism and Dissemination. *Advances in Educational Technologies and Instructional Design Book Series*, 274–297. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-6682-7.ch021>
- 16) Mineene, W.-W. N., & Kihara, A. (2023). Impact of Digital Technology Capabilities on Operational Performance of the Media Industry: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Business and Strategic Management*, 8(3), 91–108. <https://doi.org/10.47941/jbsm.1393>
- 17) Mitchell, A., Gottfried, J. A., Barthel, M., & Shearer, E. (2016). *The modern news consumer: news attitudes and practices in the digital era*. <https://apo.org.au/node/65498>
- 18) Neto, B. M., Ishikawa, E., Ghinea, G., & Grønli, T.-M. (2019). Newsroom 3.0: Managing Technological and Media Convergence in Contemporary Newsrooms. *Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.24251/HICSS.2019.290>
- 19) Newman, Nic, Fletcher, Richard, Robertson, Craig, Eddy, Katy, & Nielsen, Rasmus Kleis. (2022). *Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2022*. Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, University of Oxford. <https://reutersinstitute.politics.ox.ac.uk/digital-news-report/2022>
- 20) Nurhadiyati, N. (2024). *Revolutionizing Newsgathering: The Impact of Digital Media and New Technologies*. 85–91. <https://doi.org/10.22492/issn.2186-5906.2024.7>
- 21) O'Brien, D. (2024). 30 *The transformation of news in the digital age: Business model changes, challenges, and future directions* (pp. 431–450). De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110793444-030>
- 22) Pavlik, J. V. (2014). *Transformation: Examining the Implications of Emerging Technology for Journalism, Media and Society*. 1(1), 9–24. <https://doi.org/10.30958/AJMMC.1-1-1>
- 23) Pavlik, John V. (2013). *Innovation and the future of journalism*. *Digital Journalism*, 1(2), 181–193. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2012.756666>
- 24) Peña-Ascacibar, G., & Álvarez-Peralta, M. (2021). Emergencia, innovación y consolidación de nuevos modelos para el periodismo digital: estudio de los casos de El Confidencial, elDiario.es e infoLibre. *Estudios Sobre El Mensaje Periodístico*, 27(2), 593–606. <https://doi.org/10.5209/ESMP.71245>
- 25) Pérez-Seijo, S., Barbosa, S., & Vicente, P. N. (2023). *Artificial Intelligence in Journalism: Case Study of the Spanish, Portuguese and Brazilian News Media Systems* (pp. 261–274). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-43926-1_18
- 26) Ramzani, I., & Daud, P. M. (2024). The effect of digital transformation on organizational performance: a meta analysis. *Deleted Journal*, 15(1), 50–65. <https://doi.org/10.30996/die.v15i1.10643>
- 27) Roem, E. R., & Vanisya, W. (2024). Transformation in the digital era: optimising social media for news coverage. *Deleted Journal*, 8(3), 675–684. <https://doi.org/10.25139/jsk.v8i3.8477>
- 28) Said, A. (2023). *The Evolution of Journalism Ethics in the Digital Age: Challenges and Implications*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/23vde>
- 29) Shefontiuk, A. (2021). *Диджитальна журналістика як новий тип медіадіяльності*. 27(2), 70–76. <https://doi.org/10.28925/2311-259X.2021.2.5>

- 30) Singer, Jane B., Hermida, Alfred, Domingo, David, Heinonen, Ari, Paulussen, Steve, Quandt, Thorsten, ... & Vujnovic, Marina. (2011). *Participatory Journalism: Guarding Open Gates at Online Newspapers*. Wiley-Blackwell. [ISBN: 978-1405185830]
- 31) Sonni, A. F., Hafied, H., Irwanto, I., & Latuheru, R. D. (2024). Digital Newsroom Transformation: A Systematic Review of the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Journalistic Practices, News Narratives, and Ethical Challenges. *Journalism and Media*, 5(4), 1554–1570. <https://doi.org/10.3390/journalmedia5040097>
- 32) Sri, T., Ayu, P., Devi, P., & Kurniati, D. (2024). Digital Transformation and Impact on Organizational Change and Performance. *Journal of Economic Education and Entrepreneurship Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.62794/je3s.v5i1.3551>
- 33) Suharto, S. (2024). Challenges and Opportunities of Digital Transformation in Strategy Management. *International Journal of Science and Society*, 6(1), 620–630. <https://doi.org/10.54783/ijssoc.v6i1.1050>
- 34) Sultan, M. I., Bhuiyan, A. J. Md. S. A., & Amir, A. S. (2024). Reimagining Journalism: Exploring the AI Revolution - A Thorough Analysis of Potential Advantages and Challenges. *Komunikator*, 16(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.18196/jkm.20172>
- 35) Thurman, Neil & Schapals, Aljosha. (2017). *Automating the news: How algorithms are rewriting the media*. *Digital Journalism*, 5(8), 958–976. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2016.1208053>
- 36) Triwulan, D., Ramadhani, N., Raudatul Zannah, N. A., Naibaho, M., & Effendi, E. (2024). Tantangan Etika dalam Jurnalisme Digital: Studi Kasus Peran Media Sosial dalam Penyebaran Berita. *Da'watuna*. <https://doi.org/10.47467/dawatuna.v4i3.681>
- 37) Túnñez-López, J.-M., Fieiras-Ceide, C., & Vaz-Álvarez, M. (2021). *Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Journalism: transformations in the company, products, contents and professional profile*. 34(1), 177–193. <https://doi.org/10.15581/003.34.1.177-193>
- 38) Varfolomeeva, A. (2022). *Journalists and social media* (pp. 58–82). Routledge eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429505386-4>
- 39) Weiss, A. S., & Wulfemeyer, T. (2014). Newspapers, TV News Offer More Online Innovation: *Newspaper Research Journal*, 35(2), 100–118. <https://doi.org/10.1177/073953291403500208>
- 40) Wölker, A., & Powell, T. E. (2021). Algorithms in the newsroom? News readers' perceived credibility and selection of automated journalism: *Journalism: Theory, Practice & Criticism*, 22(1), 86–103. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1464884918757072>
- 41) Xu, J. (2024). *Exploring the Approaches and Strategies for the Transformation from Traditional News Transmission to Digital News in the New Era*. 1(3), 81–84. <https://doi.org/10.62517/jnme.202410314>
- 42) Yaroshenko, O. (2024). Artificial Intelligence in Journalism: the Future of Media under the Influence of New Technologies. *Наукові Записки Інституту Журналістики*, 2 (85), 139–156. <https://doi.org/10.17721/2522-1272.2024.85.10>